

PROBLEMS FACED BY FIRST GENERATION LEARNERS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract

Students who are first generation learners face several difficulties in pursuing and completing their basic courses. They each have their unique story about completing their university education. They have no role models within the family who can help them learn. The challenges faced by them range from psychological issues like anxiety, lack of confidence and insecurity, social issues such as not being accepted by their peers, and academic issues such as being comparatively slow or backward, requiring more tutoring and guidance to understand what is being taught. Many first-generation students' dropout being unable to survive these insurmountable challenges. We need to understand what could be changed in order to help these group of students.

INTRODUCTION

Most of the students from remote villages and towns in India are first generation learners and face various psychological challenges in their pursuit of education. First generational learners are those who are the first in their families to get a formal education whose parents or elders might or might not have gone to school. At the university level, first generational learners are those who never had a familial knowledge of university life, where the parents or elders in the family did not pursue higher education or receive a degree in life. They encounter a lot of difficulties in attending and completing their regular schooling and courses in college when compared to second generation or third generation learners. Although perhaps supportive of higher education, their parents and family members may view their entry into college as a break in the family system rather than a continuation of their schooling.

They are often considered as disadvantaged learners signifying their distinctness from the privileged. They have to endure many unpleasant experiences created by the system through their journey of navigating and surviving university education. Often these students apply to

nearby colleges or familiar colleges within their ecosystem, which may not be suitable for them in the long run. They cannot afford multiple application fees and are unsure of how to determine a good fit, as they do not have the required knowledge with respect to the choosing of an educational branch, college and course. The students have to take care of their studies and knowledge with none in the family or nearby to look up to. The lack of information among themselves is often ridiculed as “being backward” or “dull”.

The challenges faced by first-generation learners range from linguistic essentials to having difficulties in socialisation and fitting into the in-trend university aesthetics. These students lack basic knowledge in English and are incapable of producing acceptable drafts and sentences. Their work consists of many grammatical and comprehension. They share a common set of anxieties and hesitations to approach teachers for guidance as they feel insecure and helpless. Even to clear a minor doubt they have to wait for a long time and travel long distances. These students may come to college with fewer resources and more academic needs, making them targets for discrimination. Neglected by their teachers, ridiculed by their classmates, and finding little support at home are the reasons some of the students drop out in school or college within the first three years.

There are a significant number of first-generation learners in government schools and colleges in India. The reservations were put up in place for SCs, STs and OBCs to help these students. Scholarship schemes are designed such that these first-generational learners are able to sustain in the city and the university, such as helping them in day-to-day expenses for travel and accommodation. The draft National Education Policy, 2019 has put emphasis on the “functionality and fluency” for teaching English language in schools (MHRD 2019). Education of these first-generation students is a complex of challenges. It requires substantially higher commitment and lot more work, and it’s the responsibility of the teachers to make this education happen. The teachers need to recognize their dilemmas and become more receptive towards their problems. The same teachers find it relatively easier to teach their “less-disadvantaged” classmates.

It is generally assumed that learning happens only after one becomes a fairly fluent reader. If the student is not able to fairly comprehend what he or she is reading, then learning does not begin, as almost everything is from books. So, learning in any subject depends on reading. Students who learn to read later, or read slowly, may avoid reading, are unable to understand the textbooks and guidebooks, developing negative attitudes and are less likely to complete the course. Reading in turn is linked with listening and understanding in the

classroom. Reports indicate that first generational learners have lower attendance, less consistent performance, interrupted studies and low self-esteem. The role of teachers here, is to try and engage all students frequently in the classroom to make sure learning is taking place. They may even resort to the “bilingual method of teaching” i.e. using their mother tongue in order to help them familiarize with English and to make sure knowledge is being imparted.

The biggest challenge for teachers is capturing the attention of students and putting the ideas of learning language in a way that stays in their minds long after they have left the classroom. To make this happen, the classroom experience should be redefined with innovative techniques which make the learners learn enthusiastically. To make the students proficient, the way of teaching should be more practical and allow interaction between teacher and students. There should be an atmosphere created such that the students and teachers are able to interact without any hesitations.

Students may be given tasks like reading newspapers loudly, watching educational movies and documentaries in English with subtitles. Involving in model interviews, and organizing cultural plays and debates to enrich their language skills. When the students complete their tasks, they familiarize in English and overcome their fears and hesitations and develop the confidence to speak English anywhere. The teachers can listen to the speech and language of the learners and simultaneously correct their mistakes with positive affirmations. As the process continues further, the students will be able to learn English within the minimum period.

CONCLUSION

There are also first-generation students who are resilient and strive to learn and improve academically. They are aware of their challenges, and use them as a source of motivation. These students are driven and determined. They have a single-minded objective to learn and succeed in life. They can perform academically in ways that are equal to or even better than students with an educational background. Support groups and necessary guidance can help these students to improve further and can help alleviate their internal pressure and challenges they come across in order to succeed.

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